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Feature 2/2025 – Recycling the Future: Bioplastics, Policy & the New European Bioeconomy

ReBioCycle

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What is ReBioCycle?

ReBioCycle stands for "A new European #blueprint for circular bioplastics #upcycling solutions." It is an Innovation Action project focusing on biobased biodegradable polymers and plastics. ReBioCycle goals are to demonstrate that:

✓ **#biobased #biodegradable #plastics** can be kept in the cycle for as long as possible through innovative **#recycling** technologies

✓ **#endoflife #biobased #biodegradable #plastics** can be used in the **#circular #bioeconomy**

The project is funded by the [Circular Bio-based Europe Joint Undertaking \(CBE JU\)](#) and its members under the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme. ReBioCycle started on 1 October 2024 and will run for 4 years.

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The promising future of biotechnology and sustainable economy in Europe: A policy digest on the recycling of biodegradable bioplastics

A year after the European Commission communication "Building the future with nature: Boosting Biotechnology and Biomanufacturing in the EU" was published and a set of initiatives was announced in the first quarter of 2025, the future of biotechnology and sustainable economy in Europe looks a bit more promising. These sectors were then identified as key to the competitiveness and modernisation of the EU's economy.

The policy initiatives and legislative developments announced in the first quarter of 2025 deepen this sentiment and will profoundly impact the future of the EU Circular economy and competitiveness. This, in turn, will influence the field in which ReBioCycle operates, the recycling of biodegradable plastics, and innovative processes and technologies to do so.

FUTURE LOADING

What are those new initiatives and legislative developments?

- **The Competitiveness Compass:** Sets out the strategic initiative to enhance the EU's global standing by focusing on key areas such as innovation, decarbonisation, and security. The strategy takes up the main findings of the **Letta** and **Draghi** reports and proposes a more concrete implementation with flagship measures. One set of measures focuses on closing the innovation gap. By proposing action plans for advanced materials, biotech, robotics, and other key technologies, the European Commission aims to reignite its innovation engine and promote industrial leadership. The EC will also work on a Start-up and a Scale-up Strategy to address the obstacles preventing new companies from emerging and scaling up, which are some of the most frequent bottlenecks in European innovation. The EC will also publish a roadmap for decarbonisation and competitiveness to ensure the EU is an attractive location for manufacturing, promoting clean tech and new circular business models. A Decarbonisation Accelerator Act will extend accelerated permitting to sectors in transition. The compass also foresees tailor-made action plans for energy-intensive sectors, such as the chemical sector.
- **The Clean Industrial Act:** It outlines the urgent, short-term need for EU strategies to support and create optimal conditions for the European industry to regain competitiveness while decarbonising. It will help Europe achieve the objectives of the European Green Deal while improving access to affordable energy, creating lead markets, boosting demand and supply of circular materials, products and services, and strengthening economic security.

- **The Chemicals Industry Package:** The European Commission will propose targeted initiatives to enhance the sector's competitiveness and build a favourable business environment to drive growth in the chemical industry while preserving health and the environment. Later, President von der Leyen will convene a strategic dialogue on the future of the chemical industry in Europe.
- **The review of the Bioeconomy Strategy:** The **initial EU's Bioeconomy Strategy** was adopted in 2012 to address the production of renewable biological resources and their conversion into vital products and bioenergy. The Strategy was reviewed in 2018 to refocus the actions to better support the **2030 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)**, **Paris Agreement climate objectives** and new EU policy priorities. The European Commission plans to review the Bioeconomy Strategy in 2025 (Q4) to promote more circular and sustainable production, use and consumption of biological resources for food, materials, energy and services. The revision will be implemented through legislative and non-legislative acts.

PPWR Focus - Design for Recycling for biobased and biodegradable plastics

Interview with
Hasso von Pogrell
 Managing Director
 europeanbioplastics

ReBioCycle has received funding from the Circular Bio-based Joint Undertaking (JU) and its members under the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101156032. The JU receives support from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme and the Bio-based Industries Consortium

The **Packaging and Packaging Waste Regulation (PPWR)** is a cornerstone of the European Union's ambitious strategy to transition towards a circular economy. Aimed at minimising the environmental impact of packaging, the PPWR introduces stricter rules on packaging design, waste reduction, and recyclability. One of its central pillars is the **Design for Recycling (DfR) criteria**, which ensures that all packaging on the EU

market is recyclable in practice and at scale. While this shift is expected to drive innovation in conventional plastic recycling, it also poses significant implications for **biodegradable plastics**.

In this interview, we speak with Hasso von Pogrell, Managing Director at European Bioplastics and one of ReBioCycle's project partners, to explore what the new DfR framework could mean for innovation, market access, and the broader role of biodegradable plastics in Europe's circular packaging future.

Read the full interview here: <https://rebiocycle.eu/news/interview-with-hasso-von-pogrell-managing-director-at-european-bioplastic-on-ppwr-design-for-recycling/>

Harnessing Microbial Power in ReBioCycle: Enzymatic solutions for bioplastics recycling

The shift from conventional plastics to bioplastics is accelerating, driven by regulations and consumer demand. Companies must develop strategies that balance economic viability and sustainability to remain competitive, particularly regarding end-of-life solutions. With global bioplastics production expected to reach 2.98 million metric tons by 2027, waste management must evolve to support the efficient recycling of these materials. Among the leading bioplastics, #polyhydroxyalkanoates (#PHA) stand out, with a projected 16.3% market growth by 2030.

However, maximising their circularity requires advances in enzymatic recycling technologies. PHA degradation relies on PHA depolymerases, #enzymes that remain underexplored despite their potential. These enzymes target either short-chain (scl-PHA) or medium-chain (mcl-PHA) polymers and function intracellularly or extracellularly, yet their kinetic mechanisms remain poorly understood.

Expert [Laura de Eugenio](#), researcher at [Centro de Investigaciones Biológicas Margarita Salas \(CSIC\)](#), presented her work on 5 March 2025 at the II International Seminar Biotechnology in Valencia, Spain.

Watch the video below, where Laura explains her work on harnessing microbial power in ReBioCycle to recycle bioplastics.-.

Advancing enzymatic PHA recycling is key to closing the loop in bioplastic sustainability, reducing waste, and minimising environmental impact. By unlocking the full potential of depolymerases, bioplastics can become a true pillar of the circular economy.

Check out other videos about the project on our YouTube channel: <https://www.youtube.com/@ReBioCycleProject>.

ReBioCycle partner Feature: BiOrbic

BiOrbic Research Ireland Centre for Bioeconomy is Ireland's national hub for advancing a sustainable and circular bioeconomy. Headquartered at **University College Dublin**, BiOrbic brings together world-class researchers and industry partners to drive innovation in bio-based systems that reduce dependence on fossil resources and promote environmental resilience.

As a leading bioeconomy research centre, BiOrbic is actively involved in both fundamental and applied research, with a strong focus on multi-actor collaborations—such as **EU-funded projects**—that enable the scaling and demonstration of cutting-edge technologies. The centre also plays a vital role in policy engagement, helping to bridge the gap between research, industry, policy, and decision-makers.

BiOrbic is led by Professor **Kevin O'Connor**, who also coordinates the **ReBioCycle** project, ensuring strategic alignment between Ireland's national bioeconomy priorities and European circular and bioeconomy goals.

Recycling strategies for bioplastics: what's next? An overview of novel strategies by EU-Funded projects

Are you interested in exploring novel strategies for recycling bioplastics? This document presents an overview of several EU-funded projects in this field based on the workshop organised by [European Bioplastics](#) on December 9, 2024, in Berlin.

As the bioplastics market grows, it is essential to address the issue of recycling biodegradable bioplastics and to study their most effective recycling pathways to manage bioplastic products at their end of life. Bioplastic waste does not yet constitute a relevant amount of the total plastic waste (only 1% in weight).

In the past years, several projects, [BioSupPack](#) is one of them, have been funded by the Horizon Programme for Research and Innovation and the [Circular Bio-based Europe Joint Undertaking \(CBE JU\)](#) to improve and upscale bioplastics recycling technologies. Three new projects starting in 2024, [MoeBIOS](#), [ReBioCycle](#), and [Prosper Bioplastics](#), are scaling up bioplastic recycling technologies even further.

Learn more about their strategies on the proceedings document of the event in the [ReBioCycle Zenodo Community](#): <https://zenodo.org/records/14231054>.

Upcoming events

- o 30 April 2025 – *Talk with Jan Pels (TORWASH) on chemical recycling for bioplastics at EUBP Talk Series: <https://www.european-bioplastics.org/news/eubp-talk-series/eubp-talk-1-bioplastics-recycling/>*
- o 3 June 2025 – *EUBP Talk Series on Advancements in bioplastics recycling closing event, Brussels, with Jan Pels (TORWASH) and AIMPLAS*
- o 17 June 2025 – *Upcoming talk of Kevin O'Connor (UCD/BiOrbic) at the CBE JU Cluster Projects' Workshop on Bio-based materials*
- o 10 October 2025 – *Event at K Fair, Düsseldorf, Germany*
- o 15-16 October – *ReBioCycle General Assembly, Turin, Italy.*

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